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Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

Deliverable D7.2
Mid-term review report

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¹ **Nature:** R -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** **PU** -Public; **CO** -Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Executive Summary

The project has run half of its duration and continues as planned with minor deviations. All planned milestones and deliverables were executed and provided except for milestone **MS5** and deliverables **D2.3 (D4)** and **D3.1 (D5)**. However, they are all close to completion and their impact on the other tasks within the project are minimal. The most impacting deviation encountered in the project was the sudden death of the project leader, which led to a loss of managing efficiency during several months. The resulting delays are expected to be resolved throughout the remainder of the project.

The objectives described in Annex 1 of the grant agreement remain relevant, which was confirmed during the surveys taken with nuclear regulatory bodies, operators and research organizations (see deliverable **D1.1**). All partners have contributed and continue to contribute, in close collaboration with each other, to the realization of the project objectives.

The project has disseminated its results through social media, scientific literature and events, as well as in other EC funded (ENTENTE, STRUMAT-LTO, DELISA-LTO) and national projects (Kleinproben).

The financial summary after the first reporting period indicates no major deviations and all partners remain engaged to complete all deliverables as described within the grant agreement and within the agreed budget.

1 Introduction

This deliverable provides an overview of the current status of the activities of the complete project. It aims to guide the reviewers during the mid-term review meeting that takes place on 25 January 2023.

2 Project Background

The fracture toughness of a material characterizes its resistance against crack propagation and is an important design parameter to guarantee the structural integrity of components. From several fracture toughness experiments within the ductile-to-brittle transition zone, the reference temperature, T_0 , can be derived by applying the Master Curve approach. Here, T_0 defines the transition temperature for a median fracture toughness of 100 MPa·√m for a 1 inch fracture toughness specimen. It is important to note that a shift in T_0 denotes a shift in transition temperature. For example, in the framework of irradiation embrittlement of steels, the shift in T_0 provides a measure for the shift in ductile-to-brittle transition temperature (DBTT).

To assess irradiation embrittlement of reactor pressure vessel (RPV) steels, nuclear regulatory bodies base their evaluation primarily on the semi-empirical methodology based on impact tests on Charpy surveillance specimens. In the framework of long-term operation (LTO) of the present nuclear power plants, surveillance data is scarce, and irradiation space in materials test reactors (MTR) is limited and costly. In addition, the miniaturized size of the specimens limits their activity, which facilitates their handling. Therefore, the determination of irradiation embrittlement on miniaturized specimens is desirable.

Application of the Master Curve approach allows to determine T_0 and hence the shift in T_0 from different specimen sizes and geometries at different test temperatures. As such, miniature compact tension (MCT) specimens can be used to optimize irradiation space in MTR; or MCT specimens can be extracted from broken Charpy surveillance specimens. The latter can provide valuable additional data in the plant's safety case.

The present FRACTESUS project aims to determine the effect of specimen size on the fracture toughness properties. Finite element models (FEM) are used to investigate the difference between large-size and MCT specimens and quantitatively assess the resulting loss of constraint due to size reduction. The optimal range of usability of MCT specimens can therefore be determined and evidenced with experimental results. Large inter-laboratory testing is included in the FRACTESUS project in an attempt to prove the repeatability and reproducibility of the small-scale testing of fracture toughness properties. Various materials relevant for most of the available reactor materials and irradiation conditions are investigated.

3 Project Goals

The main objective of FRACTESUS is to validate the usage of small-scale fracture toughness specimen testing for safety assessment of reactor pressure vessels (RPV). The work undertaken in the project is aimed to convince appropriate authorities to use miniature compact specimens (MCT) in the Master Curve approach and finally introduce them to surveillance programs. Validation of MCT testing will be done for a wide group of RPV materials representing different properties in initial and irradiated states, typical for

various reactor designs and after the exposition to neutron irradiation. Comparison of results between MCT and large specimens supported by numerical modelling will be done and detailed guidelines of MCT testing will be prepared. Additionally, changes in codes and standard will be proposed, if necessary.

4 Project Structure

In order to structure the project, the work is broken down into work packages. The WP structure is visualized in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1 – Visualization of the Work Package structure of the FRACTESUS project.

The detailed work package and task descriptions, and financial details are provided in Annex 1 of the grant agreement and are summarized in Section 6 and Section 9, respectively.

5 Project Milestones & Deliverables

The status of all milestones and deliverables related to the FRACTESUS project are summarized in *Table 1* and *Table 2*, respectively. Milestone **MS5** (Irradiated specimens fabricated) is delayed and expected to be completed by the end of Q1 of 2023. All other due milestones were completed and the future ones are expected to be completed without major delays.

Deliverable **D3.1** (D5: First results and evaluation of fracture toughness tests on 0.16C(T) specimens) and **D2.3** (D4: Fabrication of irradiated specimens) are delayed. A first draft report for D3.1 is presently available and expected to be completed by 31-01-2023. Deliverable report D2.3 is expected to be

completed approximately one month after completion of MS5. All other due deliverables were completed and the future ones are expected to be completed without major delays.

Table 1 – Overview and status of all project milestones. The milestones are sorted following their planned delivery date.

MS	Title	Lead	Planned date	Achieved	Delivery date	Comment
MS14	Social and Scientific profiles available	UC	31-10-2020	yes	27-10-2020	
MS20	Appointment of the general assembly members	SCK CEN	31-01-2021	yes	14-12-2020	
MS3	Test matrix finalised	VTT	31-03-2021	yes	4-06-2021	
MS1	Technical memorandum concerning the current standards	SCK CEN	31-07-2021	yes	31-07-2021	
MS2	Summary of the discussions from the nuclear regulatory authorities, reactor operators and research organizations, and a list of topic areas needing to be addressed, in order of importance, to feed into T1.4 deliverable	VTT	31-07-2021	yes	19-05-2022	Due to scarce response rate for the surveys obtained in the initial phase the deadline for responses was shifted, and meanwhile, new responders were identified, causing further deadline shift.
MS15	FRACTESUS DMP, testing protocol and reporting formats defined	UC	31-07-2021	yes	31-07-2021	
MS4	Non-irradiated specimens fabricated	VTT	31-12-2021	yes	28-10-2022	Delay in unirradiated specimens fabrication is caused mostly by Covid-19 pandemic. Materials for round robin testing were distributed to all partners. MS4 is expected to be achieved to the end of 05/2022
MS6	FT tests on unirradiated materials finished	HZDR	31 Mar 2022	yes	15-12-2022	Delay in this MS achievement is caused mostly by Covid-19 restrictions imposed in all partners institutions. Due to various restrictions access to facilities was strongly limited and specimen manufacturing was delayed. A milestone report is available.
MS5	Irradiated specimens fabricated	VTT	30-06-2022	pending		The shipping of the irradiated material to participants was delayed, causing issues to scheduling with other overlapping work at the participants. The irradiated materials require special attention, and fabrication cannot be sub-contracted. Fabrication of irradiated

						specimens is ongoing and expected to be finished in Q1 of 2023 (all participants).
MS10	Numerical approach fully implemented pending experimental tests	CEA	30-09-2022	yes	15-12-2022	The round robin exercise is finished and the results are available. Hence, the numerical approach is fully implemented. A first draft of the milestone report is available. The final milestone report is expected by the end of January 2023.
MS17	First scientific paper accepted for publication	UC	30-09-2022	yes	20-01-2021	E. Altstadt et al, Nuclear Materials and Energy 26 (2021) 100918, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nme.2021.100918
MS7	FT tests on irradiated materials finished	SCK CEN	31-03-2023			
MS12	Database specified	FRA-G	31-03-2023			
MS16	First FRACTESUS special session completed	UC	31-03-2023			
MS8	Fractography on tested samples finished	NRG	30-09-2023			
MS9	Supporting tests finished	CCFE	30-09-2023			
MS11	Numerical results using / compared to experimental results	CEA	30-09-2023			
MS13	Database available for evaluation	FRA-G	30-09-2023			
MS18	FRACTESUS seminar completed	UC	30-09-2024			
MS19	Second FRACTESUS special session completed	UC	30-09-2024			

Table 2 – Overview and status of all project deliverables. The deliverables are sorted following their planned delivery date.

Deliverable		Title	Lead	Nature	Diss. Level	Planned date	Receipt date	Approval date	Status	Comment
D6.1	D18	Project profiles in social/scientific networks available	UC	DEC	PU	31-10-2020	2-11-2020	3-11-2020	Approved	
D8.1	D30	POPD - Requirement No. 1	SCK CEN	ETHICS	CO	31-10-2020	2-11-2020	3-11-2020	Approved	
D8.2	D31	NEC - Requirement No. 2	SCK CEN	ETHICS	CO	31-10-2020	2-11-2020	3-11-2020	Approved	
D7.1	D27	Project management platform	SCK CEN	DEC	PU	30-11-2020	27-11-2020	27-11-2020	Approved	
D6.8	D25	DMP	UC	ORDP	PU	31-03-2021	26-03-2021	26-03-2021	Approved	
D2.1	D2	Test matrix of FRACTESUS	VTT	R	PU	30-04-2021	4-06-2021	7-06-2021	Approved	
D6.9	D26	FRACTESUS testing protocols and reporting formats	UC	R	PU	31-07-2021	31-07-2021	2-08-2021	Approved	
D1.1	D1	Report on current status of sub size fracture toughness standards and testing, including all stakeholder concerns	NNL	R	CO	30-09-2021	20-12-2022	20-12-2022	Approved	
D2.2	D3	Fabrication of non-irradiated specimens	VTT	R	PU	31-01-2022	17-11-2022	17-11-2022	Approved	
D3.1	D5	First results and evaluation of fracture toughness tests on 0.16C(T) specimens	SCK CEN	R	CO	31-05-2022			Pending	Due to the sudden death of the coordinator HZDR has taken the lead to complete this deliverable. A draft report is available and the final report is expected by 31-01-2023

D2.3	D4	Fabrication of irradiated specimens	VTT	R	PU	31-07-2022				Pending	MS5 has been delayed and is expected to finish in Q1 of 2023 (all participants). The deliverable report is expected about 1 month after completing MS5.
D7.2	D28	Mid-term review report	SCK CEN	R	PU	31-12-2022					
D3.2	D6	Estimation of mechanical properties of unirradiated and irradiated RPV steels based on small specimen test technologies	UoB	R	CO	31-03-2023					
D5.1	D11	Database specification	FRA- G	R	CO	31-03-2023					
D6.4	D21	First FRACTESUS special session	UC	DEC	PU	31-03-2023					
D3.3	D7	Qualification of 0.16 C(T) fracture toughness testing on well characterized irradiated material	HZDR	R	CO	31-01-2024					
D4.1	D8	Report: Finite element simulations to compare C(T) and MC(T)	SCK CEN	R	CO	31-01-2024					
D4.2	D9	Report: Simulations based on small specimen test techniques	HZDR	R	CO	31-01-2024					
D5.4	D14	Comparison of fracture toughness results from standard and sub sized specimens	EK	R	CO	31-03-2024					
D5.5	D15	Manufacture and testing procedure of 0.16T C(T) specimens in transition range	HZDR	R	CO	31-03-2024					

D4.3	D10	Report: Synthesis of all numerical works	CEA	R	CO	31-03-2024				
D5.2	D12	Assessment of the UJV testing data and FEM simulations	NRI	R	CO	30-06-2024				
D5.3	D13	Summary of sub sized specimen test results - interpretation and issues (includes simple database)	FRA-G	R	CO	30-06-2024				
D5.6	D16	Summary of ongoing international activities	SCK CEN	R	PU	30-06-2024				
D5.7	D17	Guidelines for Master Curve testing with miniature specimens	CCFE	R	PU	30-09-2024				
D6.2	D19	Report on FRACTESUS communication activities	UC	R	PU	30-09-2024				
D6.3	D20	Report on FRACTESUS scientific and technical contributions	UC	R	PU	30-09-2024				
D6.5	D22	FRACTESUS seminar	UC	DEC	PU	30-09-2024				
D6.6	D23	Second FRACTESUS special session	UC	DEC	PU	30-09-2024				
D6.7	D24	Report on FRACTESUS training and education activities	UC	R	PU	30-09-2024				
D7.3	D29	Final review report	SCK CEN	R	PU	30-09-2024				

Dissemination level: PU – Public; CO – Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Nature: R – Document, report; DEC – Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; ETHICS – Ethics requirement; ORDP – Open Research Data Pilot

6 Project Status

6.1 WP1 – Stakeholder involvement

6.1.1 Main objectives

The main objectives of this work package can be summarized as:

Objective 1.1: To set up a Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) and End User Group (EUG) to provide expertise throughout the FRACTESUS program, and to assess whether the information produced as part of WP1 is appropriate to inform future work packages.

Objective 1.2: To understand the content and limitations of current standards (ISO, CEN, ASTM, JEAC...) on fracture toughness testing on sub-sized specimens, and implement the output of WP5 (Evaluation and Guidelines) in Standards Development.

Objective 1.3: To understand the concerns of the various European (and other) nuclear regulators

Objective 1.4: To understand the current extent of use of sub-sized specimens in fracture toughness testing by operators and research organisations, and identify and concerns or gaps in knowledge.

Objective 1.5: To record the current extent of usage, concerns, knowledge gaps arising from all stakeholders (from current standards/standard committees, nuclear regulators, operators and researchers) in order that these can be addressed in subsequent work packages.

6.1.2 Progress summary

Objective 1.1: SAC and EUG successfully set up.

Objective 1.2: ‘Technical Memo Concerning the Current Standards’ issued. In this, current International Standards used for testing small C(T) specimens in different countries have been reported, and the features of those standards which address aspects of acquiring toughness data which are affected by specimen size and geometry have been highlighted. Any limitations of the current Standards with respect to small specimens have been identified and reported. With this report milestone **MS1** was completed.

Objective 1.3 and Objective 1.4: A Memo entitled ‘Survey to Nuclear Regulators, Operators and Research Organizations’ issued. This report includes opinions on sub-sized specimen fracture toughness testing and extent of use/reliance on using sub-sized compact tension specimen fracture toughness test data. With this report milestone **MS2** was completed.

Objective 1.5: Deliverable **D1.1 (D1)** titled ‘Overall output: Stakeholder Involvement’ was issued in May 2022, which provides an overall summary of all tasks completed in WP1.

6.1.3 Task details

Task 1.1: Scientific Advisory Committee and End User Group

The SAC and EUG were set up and had a successful meeting to discuss the programme. The output comprises the minutes of the SAC/EUG meeting that produced excellent discussion and feedback.

Task 1.2: Current Standards

A detailed report entitled ‘Technical Memo Concerning the Current Standards’ was delivered by M. Lambrecht (SCK CEN), S. Ortner (NNL) and M. Serrano-Garcia (CIEMAT). This report summarizes the current standard practices concerning fracture toughness measurements adopted in different countries, with a more detailed discussion on the size requirements for valid measurements of fracture properties in the ASTM and ISO standards. The issues, consequences and limitations associated with miniaturizing toughness specimens was also discussed.

Task 1.3(a and b): Nuclear Regulatory Viewpoint and Current Extent of Use by Operators/Research Organizations

The task considers the nuclear regulatory viewpoint of small-scale testing, as well as the current extent of their use by operators and researchers around the world. A survey was prepared to collate the viewpoints of nuclear regulators, operators and research organizations of the following countries: France, Belgium, UK, Germany, Switzerland, Sweden, Finland, Spain, Czech Republic, Hungary and the US. This survey asked the ‘extent to which regulations and Code/Standards (C&S) applicable to your country allow the use of Master Curve based techniques in support of reactor vessel integrity assessment and the establishment of a pressure temperature operating limit’ and whether their institution was ‘aware of the possibility of using mini-CR specimens (MCT), instead of large specimens to support Master Curve applications’ and any concerns they had. Responses were collated, stakeholder concerns documented (including, amongst others, thickness corrections, size effects and material inhomogeneity) and reported in Milestone 1.4 ‘Survey to Nuclear Regulators, Operators and Research Organizations’. The SAC and EUG have provided feedback on this task, which included whether mini-C(T) testing will likely become an additional requirement rather than a replacement (therefore incurring additional costs) as well as a discussion around acceptance of the Master Curve methodology.

Task 1.4: Overall Output

The task is concerned with the overall output of WP1: Stakeholder Involvement. This deliverable was issued in May 2022 with contributions from SCK CEN, NNL and VTT. Deliverable **D1.1 (D1)** brings together contributions from all parties in one document. The role of the SAC/EUG, current fracture toughness standards used around the world, the viewpoints and concerns of nuclear regulatory bodies, operators and research organizations are all discussed, with recommendations on how FRACTESUS can be used to address such concerns given.

6.2 WP2 – Materials selection and fabrication of specimens

6.2.1 Main objectives

The main objectives of this work package are summarized by three tasks:

Task 2.1: Selection of materials for both irradiated and non-irradiated specimens

Task 2.2: Validation of pre-test measurements, comparability of specimens fabricated in different locations, fabrication of non-irradiated specimens

Task 2.3: Validation of fabrication of irradiated specimens, comparability of specimens fabricated in different facilities, fabrication of irradiated specimens

6.2.2 Progress summary

VTT is leading this work package and most consortium members participate in this WP. The progress can be summarized as follows.

Task 2.1: The test matrix for both irradiated and non-irradiated materials was determined in milestone **MS3** and is described in deliverable report **D2.1 (D2)**. The deliverable report provides a detailed description of all specifications of the project's test matrix. Thus, this task has been successfully completed.

Task 2.2: All irradiated and non-irradiated materials have been distributed to the participating laboratories. All unirradiated specimens have been successfully machined, thereby completing **MS4**. The full description of their fabrication and the final specimen dimensions of each participant is described in deliverable **D2.2 (D3)**. Thus, this task has been successfully completed.

Task 2.3: The fabrication of irradiated specimens is ongoing and the majority of the specimens are expected to be finished in Q1 of 2023 (**MS5**). The shipping of the irradiated material to participants was delayed, causing issues to scheduling with other overlapping work at the participants' laboratories. Thus, both **MS5** and **D2.3 (D4)** are delayed, with the deliverable report expected one month after completion of the milestone. The progress of the specimen fabrication is closely monitored via periodic surveys.

6.2.3 Task details

Task 2.1: Material selection

Participants were initially surveyed for available materials, specimen design, fabrication methods (VTT → all participants). The information was compiled and reviewed (VTT) with respect to the findings in WP1 and the project objectives. Then, the partners were surveyed again for their personal interests and the general value they foresaw with the investigation of each material (VTT → all participants).

Several meetings were held with the participating laboratories to agree on material selections and the limits on the specimen design. The test matrix was finalised in 2021 (VTT, with assistance from SCK CEN and HZDR) and is reported in **D2.1 (D2)** (VTT).

All materials selected in FRACTESUS portray steels with relevance to the European nuclear power industry. In addition, the materials are representative for both eastern and western reactor pressure vessel materials. A sufficiently large database of previous fracture toughness results with larger specimens was identified for each material.

In the interlaboratory study for the unirradiated materials, the materials cover a wide range of reference temperatures T_0 (-104 ... +8 °C), various chemical compositions such as A533B LUS (JSPS) with a high P and S content, as well as different fabrication techniques with plates, forgings and weldments.

In terms of the irradiated materials, both 73W and 15Kh2MFAA in the test matrix can also be compared to their unirradiated state. In addition, 15Kh2MFAA is investigated in different irradiation and annealing states.

The specimen design is limited to subsized compact tension specimens. However, the partners use their own specimen designs and test setups, provided that they fulfil the ASTM E1921 standard requirements. Discrepancies in the interlaboratory study results may then reveal possible effects of the differences. No

specimen side grooving was applied, since the positive impact for small specimens is small and the negative effect on measuring capacity is large.

Task 2.2: Fabrication of unirradiated specimens

The providers of each material (HZDR, NRI, SCK-CEN, CIEMAT, FRA-G) shipped them to the corresponding testing partners in the interlaboratory exercises. Participants successfully fabricated and fatigue pre-cracked miniature compact tension specimens from unirradiated materials in accordance to the test matrix (all participants).

The participants were surveyed for their experiences and any other remarks they may have during specimen preparation (VTT → all participants). The deliverable report **D2.2 (D3)** covers the fabrication of the materials, including the final specimen dimensions of the participants as well as experiences and remarks from the survey.

The surveys illustrated that apart from some workshop issues, most challenges in specimen preparation were related to fatigue pre-cracking. These challenges remain a topic of discussion and will be investigated further. Some guidance on the matter will then be provided to WP5.

Task 2.3: Fabrication of irradiated specimens

The provider of the inter-laboratory study material (SCK CEN) shipped it to the partners in the interlaboratory exercise. Fabrication of irradiated specimens is ongoing and is expected to be finished in Q1 of 2023 (all participants). The participants were surveyed for progress and experiences in November 2022 (VTT), with an additional survey following in early 2023 for the yet unfinished partners.

So far, 2 out of 7 participants have finished irradiated specimen fabrication for the interlaboratory study. In addition, FRA-GER has fabricated and tested their ANP-4 material. So far, no issues have been reported concerning the exercise. However, one partner has indicated a change of their specimen design and manufacturing method, due to the unacceptable fabrication quality and dimensions of the specimens. All details will be provided in deliverable **D2.3 (D4)**, which will follow milestone **MS5**.

6.3 WP3 – Fracture mechanics testing and post-test analysis

6.3.1 Main objectives

The main objectives of this work package are summarized as:

Objective 3.1: Demonstration of fracture mechanics characterization of RPV steels by means of small specimens test technology

Objective 3.2: Qualification of 0.16 CT fracture toughness testing under hot cell conditions

Objective 3.3: Explore the fractographic peculiarities of tested 0.16 CT specimens

6.3.2 Progress summary

HZDR is leading this work package and most consortium members participate in this WP. The progress can be summarized as follows.

Objective 3.1: A large number of mini-CT based FT tests on unirradiated materials have been performed. Thereby the general applicability of the mini-CT technique for the evaluation of the reference temperature, T_0 , was demonstrated. Peculiarities associated with small specimen size have been addressed. The majority of the tests have been completed and hence milestone **MS6** was completed. A

draft of the associated deliverable report **D3.1 (D5)** is available and its completion is expected by 31-01-2023.

Objective 3.2: The work related to this objective has been started only recently; achievements or conclusions cannot yet be reported.

Objective 3.3: The work related to this objective is on going. A structured fractography procedure for mini-CT specimens is available.

6.3.3 Task details

The work package objectives will be achieved through the following tasks.

Task 3.1: Fracture mechanics testing of mini-CT specimens on unirradiated RPV steels

Milestone MS6 associated to this task is achieved, even though some test results are still pending. The first version of deliverable **D3.1 (D5)** was issued on 15/12/2022 and planned to be formally submitted by 31/01/2023.

The progress details on this task can be summarized as:

- SCK CEN: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on 15Kh2MFAA, 73W, SA508 Cl.3, ANP-5, A533B LUS (all planned tests completed)
- NRI: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on 15Kh2MFAA, A533B-JRQ (all planned tests completed)
- VTT: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on 15Kh2MFAA, 73W (all planned tests completed)
- FRA-G: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on ANP-5 (all planned tests completed)
- HZDR: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on 15Kh2MFAA, 73W, A533B JRQ, ANP-5 (all planned tests completed)
- KIT: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on SA508 Cl.3 (all planned tests completed)
- BZN: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on A533B-JRQ (all planned tests completed)
- EK-CER (in-kind): Completed mini-CT based FT test series on 15Kh2MFAA (all planned tests completed)
- NRG: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on SA508 Cl.3 (all planned tests completed)
- CIEMAT: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on SA508 Cl.3 (tests on 73W delayed)
- UC: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on ANP-5, A533B-LUS (all planned tests completed)
- PSI: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on A533B-JRQ (all planned tests completed)
- UoB: Mini-CT based FT test series on 73W and SA508 Cl.3 delayed
- CCFE: Mini-CT based FT test series on A533B-JRQ and ANP-5 delayed
- CRIEPI (in-kind): Completed mini-CT based FT test series on 15Kh2MFAA, A533B-JRQ, A533B LUS (all planned tests completed)
- CNL (in-kind): Mini-CT based FT test series on 15Kh2MFAA delayed

Task 3.2: Fracture mechanics testing of mini-CT specimens on neutron-irradiated RPV steels

The progress details on this task can be summarized as:

- Materials for the irradiated round robin (73W) were received by all participating partners
- The participants are (irr. RR): SCK CEN, VTT, HZDR, EK-CER, NRI, CEA, NRG
- The material provider is: SCK CEN
- Specimen fabrication is on-going (see WP2)
- Testing is foreseen in reporting period 2 (according to the DoW)
- FRA-G: Completed mini-CT based FT test series on their own material (ANP-4)

Task 3.3: Fractography on tested samples (unirradiated and irradiated)

The progress details on this task can be summarized as:

- NNL: Elaboration of a fractography procedure (Tech Memo) – lead
- HZDR: Elaboration of a fractography procedure (Tech Memo), report on fractography of ANP-5 and 73W, transfer of the tested JRQ sample to STUBA
- NRG: Report on fractography of SA508 Cl.3
- STUBA: Report on fractography of A533B-JRQ
- CRIEPI (in-kind): transfer of tested 15Kh2MFAA samples to CNL

Task 3.4: Supporting experiments based on small specimen test techniques (In-kind)

The progress details on this task can be summarized as:

- HZDR: Small punch test on unirradiated and irradiated RPV steels are published in NME
- CIEMAT: Small punch tests on unirradiated SA508 Cl.3 are on-going
- UC: Planned activities are in preparation
- CCFE: Planned activities (SPT, Depth sensing hardness) are in preparation
- BZN: Planned activities (Depth sensing hardness) are in preparation
- SCK CEN: Planned activities (DCT based FT tests on E97) are in preparation

6.4 WP4 –Modelling in support of WP3

6.4.1 Main objectives

The present work package is purely numerical, where the simulation tools will provide support for the exploitation, understanding and analysis of the experimental results of WP3, in order to provide interpretation and recommendations for standardization. Foremost, the work of WP4 must support experiments, to help demonstrate the relevance of the use of mini-CTs to safety authorities.

The objectives are summarized by two task.

Task 4.1 concerns the simulation of CT4 specimens, in support of the experimental investigations of WP3, specifically tasks 3.1 and 3.2. The aim is to provide a robust modelling strategy for the interpretation of the experimental data, and to provide recommendations and limitations concerning the use of these small specimens. The approach is to use finite element simulations with Local Approach of Fracture to support the interpretation of the experimental program of WP3. This process will take place in two successive stages:

- First, the objective is to set up all the numerical tools within the framework of a round robin leading to *Subtask 4.1.1*. Here, the objective will not be to compare with the experimental results, but to prepare and to compare the tools and numerical methods between the different institutes, in order to verify the consistency when analyzing the experimental results.
- The next stage is to apply this numerical approach to the experimental results to facilitate their interpretation and ultimately to provide recommendations for the user, with the aim of standardization.

Task 4.2 concerns the simulation of small specimen test techniques in support of the experimental investigations of WP3 task 3.4. The aim is to help interpreting the experimental results of small punch tests, ball indentation tests, or micro hardness tests, especially on irradiated materials.

The organization of WP4 in terms of task and subtasks is illustrated in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2 – General WP4 organisation.

6.4.2 Progress summary

CEA is leading this work package and ten consortium members participate in this WP. The progress can be summarized as follows.

Regarding deliverables and milestones (see Section 5), each institute has to write two progress reports: the first **MS10** at month 24, and the second **MS11** at month 36. From these individual reports, two deliverable reports will be produced by month 40: **D4.1 (D8)** concerning Task 4.1 and the other **D4.2 (D9)** concerning Task 4.2. All these studies will then be combined into the final deliverable report **D4.3 (D10)** at month 44.

At the end of 2020, the tasks of all the participants had been organized and harmonized in a report that synthesized all the proposals retained in the framework of WP4. The partners were invited to present the progress of their work in three progress meetings, which took place on 23 April 2021, 22 November 2021 and 11 May 2022. These regular progress updates are detailed in the meeting minutes.

The round robin (RR) exercise, associated to *Task 4.1.1*, was performed in the first reporting period. Two specimen geometries (1T-CT and MCT) and two material states (-100°C and 23°C) were considered. It was necessary to define precisely the requirements for RR models and their output to assure an unambiguous problem definition as well as make the direct comparison of the results possible without additional post processing of data delivered by all the participants.

With the finalization of the RR, all codes have been benchmarked and are ready for use in support of the experiments. Hence, milestone **MS10** is satisfied. At present, a draft report is available that will be completed by the end of January 2023.

6.4.3 Task details

Task 4.1: Fracture mechanics simulations using C(T) specimens

All results (specifically *Task 4.1.1* Numerical round robin) and all future proposals are detailed in the individual reports for each participant.

The macro- and micro-results of the round robin participants have been collected, synthesized and compared, by superimposing the results from a macroscopic point of view (evolutions of the load, the plastic volume and the stress intensity factor, as a function of the pin displacement) on the one hand, and from a point of view of local mechanical fields (maximal principal stress, equivalent plastic strain, stress triaxiality) on the other hand.

Some partners provided additional interesting results during the numerical round robin: J calculation (UJV, BZN, PSI), pin modelling (KTU). All results are summarized in milestone report **MS10**.

Task T4.2: Supporting simulations based on small specimen test techniques

This task has just started and will intensify as experimental data becomes available.

6.5 WP5 – Evaluation and guidelines

6.5.1 Main objectives

The main objectives of this work package are:

- Summarize, discuss and evaluate the test and simulation results
- Provide a detailed comparison of results from sub-sized and standard-sized specimen
- Develop best practice guidelines
- Establish links to other on-going research activities

To achieve these objectives the following tasks were defined:

Task 5.1: Interpretation of results (MTA-EK)

Task 5.2: Guidelines (SCK CEN)

Task 5.3: Exchange with ongoing projects (CIEMAT)

6.5.2 Progress summary

FRA-G is leading this work package and most consortium members participate in this WP. The progress can be summarized as follows.

Task 5.1: The progress of this task is summarized as,

- Preparation of an excel based database for internal use (the action is on-going)
- General Assembly decision: Experimental data will be made available open access at the latest by the end of the project → See data management plan (WP6)
- The work will intensify as soon as more experimental results become available

Task 5.2: The progress of this task is summarized as,

- Currently only few input data is available
- Work in this task will intensify as soon as more experience from manufacturing and testing becomes available

Task 5.3: The progress of this task is summarized as,

- Several potential projects were identified to exchange experience and results
- Exchange with the project STRUMAT-LTO is initiated (presented during Executive Committee Meeting in February 2022)
- Exchange with the German national project “Kleinproben” is initiated (presented during the 2Y Progress meeting in November 2022)
- Exchange with DELISA-LTO is planned

- Closer exchange with ENTENTE is planned

6.5.3 Task details

Task 5.1: Interpretation of results

This task concerns the interpretation of the results generated in WP3 and WP4. A detailed comparison of the fracture toughness results from standard and the sub-sized specimens is performed with the focus on characteristic values-, scatter and irradiation induced shifts of the transition temperature. The finite element results are used to interpret and explain the findings.

The testing in WP 3 as well as the simulations in WP 4 are still ongoing at the time this report was written. So far, only preliminary results from the test campaign were provided for first evaluations. The results of all participants will be provided in the form of a unified excel template generated by the University of Cantabria in WP6.

An excel based database was created (currently in draft) to summarize all experimental data (not just the final results). This database is intended for FRACTESUS internal use only.

During the General Assembly in November 2022, it was decided that the final results will be made available using open access at the latest by the end of the project (see also the revised data management plan in WP6).

The workload in this task will increase as soon as more results from WP3 and WP4 become available.

Task 5.2: Guidelines

This task addresses the elaboration of guidelines for the testing procedure including fatigue pre-cracking, side grooving, and the selection of test temperature, COD measurements and specimen orientation. The guidelines will be used to initiate an exchange with safety authorities and standardisation bodies to contribute to an efficient and unified implementation of the guidelines throughout the European nuclear industry.

This task also relies on the input from the work performed in WP2, WP3 and WP4. Currently little input is available. As far as side grooving is concerned, it was decided in WP2 that within this project all C(T) specimens shall be manufactured without side grooves. This decision was taken based on experience from partners gained outside the project. An evaluation after testing will be made to reflect on this decision and judge if a general recommendation evolves out of it.

The workload in this task will increase as soon as more results become available.

Task 5.3: Exchange with ongoing Projects

This task is dedicated to establish links with ongoing national and international activities with the focus on ongoing round robins to allow for a scientific driven exchange of experience and results, whenever possible.

During the first project meetings, a list of currently ongoing projects with a potential interest in the work of FRACTESUS and vice versa was generated by the project partners and contact persons were identified. An e-mail containing the basic information of Fractesus was sent to these contacts by CIEMAT and Framatome to establish a rudimentary link and to identify possible exchanges.

SCK CEN initiated a more intensified exchange with the EU project **STRUMAT-LTO**, which aims at closing research gaps in nuclear reactor ageing mechanisms, specifically focusing on reactor pressure vessel (RPV) embrittlement – one of the main causes affecting the long term operation of nuclear reactors. A presentation of the STRUMAT-LTO scope of work was given by its project leader Murthy Kolluri during the 4th Fractesus Executive Committee meeting.

In return, Fractesus was also presented during a STRUMAT-LTO meeting. Further cooperation is planned based on these first introductory presentations. For example, a combined session during 2023s PVP conference.

An exchange with the German national project “**Kleinproben**” (Small-scale specimen) was also initiated. This project is basically comparable to Fractesus but on a smaller, national scale. The project was presented during the 2Y progress meeting in November 2022. Since this project was already finished in September 2022, an exchange can only happen in one direction. The project “Kleinproben” partners agreed to share the experimental results with the Fractesus community.

During the 2Y progress meeting, it was agreed to have an exchange with the project **DELISA-LTO**, which mainly focuses on the analysis of structural materials from the decommissioned Jaslovské Bohunice NPP. Experimental activities using miniaturized CT specimens are planned, which makes this project another perfect candidate for exchange of experience. The exchange itself is planned for 2023.

A connection with the project **ENTENTE** already exists (Martha Serano) and discussions within FRACTESUS to use the ENTENTE platform for the distribution of the final results took place. A closer exchange is foreseen in 2023 as well.

6.6 WP6 – Dissemination, training and education and data management

6.6.1 Main objectives

The main objectives of this work package are summarized as:

Objective 6.1: To communicate the activities and the achievements of the FRACTESUS project, and to interact with different groups of interest.

Objective 6.2: To disseminate the knowledge and expertise generated along the project.

Objective 6.3: To provide training and education to both the scientific community and the industry, and to create European expert knowledge in fracture testing using sub-sized specimens.

Objective 6.4: To ensure a sound use of the experimental results, avoiding misinterpretations and inadmissible variability of the results caused by different laboratories or experimental procedures.

Objective 6.5: To make available such experimental data to the scientific community following the FAIR principles, so that further additional research can be performed in the future.

6.6.2 Progress summary

Objective 6.1:

Project profiles in the main social networks are available (deliverable **D6.1 (D18)**, milestone **MS14**): Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and ResearchGate, as is gathered in the corresponding deliverable **D6.1 (D18)**.

Significant traffic in these networks has demonstrated the public's interest in FRACTESUS. A popular platform to show project development to the general public is Twitter, where the project has obtained 7187 impressions, 5020 profile visits, 49 tweets and 19 followers (December 2022).

Twitter link: <https://twitter.com/fractesus>

In order to connect with a more professional sector, a profile was created on LinkedIn. Since then, the project has gathered 10917 impressions, 678 visits, 24 posts and 57 followers (December 2022).

LinkedIn profile: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/fractesus-h2020/>

Another common social media is Facebook, in this site Fractesus has got 1840 reaches, 28 publications, 62 engagements and 11 followers (until December 2022).

Facebook page: <https://www.facebook.com/Fractesus-H2020-100313765184397>

Since the launch of the ResearchGate profile, a generally scientific social media platform, the project has obtained 187 reads, 12 updates, 2 recommendations and 12 followers (December 2022).

ResearchGate site: <https://www.researchgate.net/project/FRACTESUS-FRACTure-mechanics-TEsting-of-irradiated-RPV-steels-by-means-of-SUB-sized-Specimens>

Additionally, contacts have been established with other H2020 projects. The main results have been a common agreement with **STRUMAT-LTO** project (grant agreement No 945272) with the aim of organising a common seminar by the end of both projects (autumn 2024), the participation in the **INCEFA-SCALE** project (grant agreement No 945300) training seminar (September 2023), providing an overview of the FRACTESUS project, and the use of the **ENTENTE** project (grant agreement No 900018) database to upload FRACTESUS experimental data.

Objective 6.2:

Concerning knowledge dissemination, the project developed the first open-access paper, which has been published in a JCR (Q1) journal and corresponds to project milestone **MS17**. Additionally, two journal papers are under review, the project was presented in eight international conferences and one national one, leading to nine proceedings papers (6 indexed in Scopus). With the aim of continuing this dissemination activity, six contributions to conferences have been prepared for the upcoming months.

All produced and upcoming scientific output related to the project are summarized in Section 8.

Objective 6.3:

A special session has been agreed with the organising committee of the ASME PVP 2023 Pressure Vessels and Piping Conference (Atlanta, USA, July 2023). Five abstracts were sent and have been accepted so far. All the work will be completed by the expected date (month 30) of the corresponding deliverable **D6.4 (D21)** and milestone **MS16**, although the session itself will be held in month 34.

Concerning FRACTESUS' final seminar (deliverable **D6.5 (D22)** and milestone **MS18**), it is expected in month 48. However, as mentioned above, with the aim of creating synergies and optimising resources and impact, it will be part of a joint event to be organised together with the STRUMAT-LTO project.

Finally, it is also worth mentioning that there is one on-going PhD Thesis at the University of Cantabria (PhD candidate: Mr. Marcos Sánchez) directly related with FRACTESUS activities.

Objective 6.4:

A general testing protocol (deliverable **D6.9 (D26)** and milestone **MS15**) to be followed within the experimental activities and common formats for reporting results was designed and successfully completed.

Objective 6.5:

In order to provide adequate data management of the data generated in the project, the Data Management Plan (DMP) (deliverable **D6.8 (D25)** and milestone **MS15**) was defined and has been periodically updated. DPM accomplishes with FAIR principles and it has been reviewed following the project necessities. At present three versions are available, with the last version explicitly mentioning that all must be publically available the latest by the end of the project.

An Open Access Procedure has been designed and agreed to ensure maximum dissemination under open access conditions of the project achievements. It includes the open access requirements and how to publish an article in the FRACTESUS framework. This procedure concerns peer-reviewed papers and other documents in a) open-access journals; b) non-open access journals; c) open-access conferences; d) non-open access conferences; and e) datasets. In this sense, FRACTESUS sections are available both in Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org>) and OpenAIRE infrastructure (<https://www.openaire.eu>), which include the open-access documents and data generated by the project, following the guidelines established by the FRACTESUS Open Access Procedure:

<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=fractesus>

<https://explore.openaire.eu/search/find?resultbestaccessright=%22Open%2520Access%22&fv0=fractesus&f0=q&active=result>

Finally, as mentioned above, experimental data will be also be open-access through the ENTENTE project database. Therefore, FRACTESUS data will be made open-access through Zenodo-OpenAIRE and through the ENTENTE database.

6.6.3 Task details

Task 6.1 Communication and dissemination

All the activities foreseen in the project proposal have been met in time, with results beyond the initial objectives. Profiles in social/scientific networks open and active, first scientific (JCR) paper published (contribution from HZDR), a total number of seven indexed (Scopus) papers published so far (contributions from UC, SCK CEN, CEA, HZDR, KTU, NNL, Framatome, VTT, ÚJV Řež, CIEMAT), nine contributions to international conferences (contributions from contributions from UC, SCK-CEN, CEA, HZDR, KTU, UC, NNL, Framatome, VTT, ÚJV Řež, CIEMAT), one contribution to national event (contribution from UC). See Section 8 for the overview.

Task 6.2 Training and education

The expected dates of the corresponding activities (as well as the deliverables and milestones) are beyond the period covered by this review procedure. However, it is important to note that preliminary works are on going. Thus, concerning the project final seminar, it has been agreed to organise a joint event with STRUMAT-LTO project. Additionally, concerning the first special session of the project in an international

event (contributors: UC, SCK CEN, CEA, HZDR, KTU, NNL, Framatome, VTT, ÚJV Řež, CIEMAT), contacts and agreement was achieved with the ASME PVP 2023 Conference (July 2023), and abstracts have been sent and accepted (contributors: UC, SCK-CEN, CEA, HZDR, KIT, NNL, Framatome, VTT, ÚJV Řež, CIEMAT).

Furthermore, there is one PhD student developing the corresponding program at the University of Cantabria and covering part of the research performed within FRACTESUS (contributors: UC).

Task 6.3 Data management

Within this task, the different documents established in the project proposal and the grant agreement have been completed (contributors: UC, SCK CEN, MTK EK, KTU):

- Data Management Plan (DMP), accomplishing with FAIRness conditions.
- FRACTESUS testing protocol.
- Reporting formats for test results, and storage of experimental files in the project webpage private area.

Additionally, the testing results are being made open-access, both internally through the SharePoint, and externally, through Zenodo-OpenAIRE and the ENENTE database. This action could also be considered (and it is) a dissemination activity, but as long as it is more related with making available raw data, it is included here as a data management activity (limiting dissemination activities to those on which results are not only presented, but also analysed and discussed) (contributors: UC, SCK CEN, MTK EK, KTU).

6.7 WP7 – General management

6.7.1 Objectives

This work package provides a clear framework and all necessary support mechanisms to enable a smooth project workflow. SCK CEN is responsible for the coordination of all R&D activities, and carrying out diverse administrative (progress reports, deliverables) and financial (fund distribution, monitoring of expenses) tasks; smooth exchange of information between the involved parties; timely submission of high-quality deliverables to the EC; and effective handling of problems (administrative, financial, ethical).

To reach these objectives, the work package is divided into three tasks:

Task 7.1: Website (public + member)

Task 7.2: Administration (deliverables, milestones, financial reporting)

Task 7.3: Meetings (executive meetings, progress meetings, general assembly)

6.7.2 Progress summary

Task 7.1: The public website and restricted management platform (SharePoint) have been created. Hence, deliverable **D7.1 (D27)** is satisfied.

Task 7.2: The table with deliverables and Milestones are summarized in Section 8. All foreseen deliverables and milestones have been delivered except for **D3.1 (D5)**, **D2.3 (D4)**, **MS06**, **MS05** and **MS10**. The reasons for these delays and present status is described in the corresponding work packages of the present report. Periodic reporting corresponding to the first period (01-10-2020 – 31-03-2022) was successfully completed.

Task 7.3: Virtual and physical meetings have been organized at regular intervals.

6.7.3 Task details

Task 7.1: Website (public + member)

The management platform was created consisting of:

- the publicly available webpage (<https://fractesus-h2020.eu>)
- the SharePoint with restricted access for project partners (<https://extranet.sckcen.be/sites/fractesus>).

In the FRACTESUS SharePoint separate sections were prepared with differentiated access levels for coordinator, partners, SAC and EUG. Besides the formal read only documents, e.g., deliverables, meeting slides and minutes also a dedicated working space was provided for each WP. In particular, results from mechanical testing of miniaturized specimens (WP3) a numerical modelling (WP4) are stored there. The details about the management platform are provided in deliverable **D7.1 (D27)**.

Task 7.2: Administration (deliverables, milestones, financial reporting)

Amendment AMD-900014-6 related to correction of references to EURATOM program from 2014-2018 to 2019-2020 in the Grant Agreement was signed in May 2021.

The status of all deliverables and milestones are provided in Section 5 of this report. An overview of the financials is provided in Section 9.

Task 7.3: Meetings (executive meetings, progress meetings, general assembly)

Up to November 2022, all the project meetings were organized virtually and were hosted by SCK CEN. The progress meeting of 8-9 November 2022 was held in person in Mol, Belgium and was hosted by SCK CEN. The following formal meetings were organized:

- Kick-off meeting (06-07/10/2020) – Virtual
- General Assembly (14/12/2020) – Virtual
- Executive Committee meeting (10/02/2021) – Virtual
- Executive Committee meeting (26/05/2021) – Virtual
- Executive Committee meeting (16/09/2021) – Virtual
- 1Y Progress Meeting and General Assembly (13-14/10/2021) – Virtual
- Executive Committee meeting (08/02/2022) – Virtual
- Executive Committee meeting (26-30/09/2022) – Virtual, individual consultations of the WP leaders by the interim coordinator
- 2Y Progress Meeting (8-9/11/2022) – In person, Lakehouse, Mol, Belgium
- General Assembly (9/11/2022) – Hybrid Virtual and in person, Lakehouse, Mol, Belgium

Additional informal technical meetings devoted to discussions on particular WP were held (virtually).

Due to the sudden death of the project leader (Tomasz Brynk), no executive committee meetings were held in Q2 of 2022. During the general assembly of 09/01/2022, the new coordinator (Giovanni Bonny) was appointed and an updated data management plan was voted (for details see WP6 in this report).

6.8 WP8 – Ethics requirements

6.8.1 Objectives

This work package sets out the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with. The two requirements are summarized in two deliverables:

D8.1: POPD – Requirement No. 1

D8.2: NEC – Requirement No. 2

6.8.2 Progress summary

D8.1: The deliverable was submitted and approved

D8.2: The deliverable was submitted and approved

6.8.3 Task details

D8.1: POPD - Requirement No. 1

The host institution must confirm that it has appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research. For host institutions not required to appoint a DPO under the GDPR a detailed data protection policy for the project must be kept on file (to be specified in the grant agreement).

Deliverable **D8.1 (D30)** was submitted and approved.

D8.2: NEC - Requirement No. 2

In case activities undertaken in non-EU countries raise ethics issues, the applicants must ensure that the research conducted outside the EU is legal in at least one EU Member State. This must be specified in the grant agreement. Copies of import/export authorizations, as required by national/EU legislation must be kept on file (to be specified in the grant agreement).

Deliverable **D8.2 (D31)** was submitted and approved.

7 Project Deviations

In *Table 3* an overview of all encountered deviations and their expected impact on the project are described. As shown, all delays are manageable and are expected to be compensated for in the next two years before the end of the project.

Table 3 – Summary of the deviations encountered during execution of the project.

WP1	
<i>Task 1.4: Overall Output</i>	
Explanation/ Reason	The deliverable D1.1 (D1) was delayed due to delayed responses to the questionnaires of nuclear regulatory bodies, operators and research organizations.

Impact on other tasks	None.
Impact on resources	None
Impact on planning	None
Corrective Action/ Contingency	The deliverable was submitted with delay.
WP2	
<i>Task 2.1: Material selection</i>	
Explanation/ Reason	The deliverable D2.1 (D2) was delayed due to constrained human resources.
Impact on other tasks	The project schedule was hindered considerably. The test matrix was communicated to the participants in the draft format, and as such, the participants had the opportunity to prepare for the next steps in the project program.
Impact on resources	None
Impact on planning	None
Corrective Action/ Contingency	The deliverable was submitted two months late.
<i>Task 2.2: Fabrication of unirradiated specimens</i>	
Explanation/ Reason	The milestone MS4 and deliverable D2.2 (D3) were delayed. The milestone not being ticked was a human error. Concerning the deliverable, the human resources were constrained at all stages. The sudden passing of the project leader caused further delays.
Impact on other tasks	The impact on testing in WP3 was limited, since the fabrication of specimens by each participant progressed in time.
Impact on resources	None

Impact on planning	None
Corrective Action/ Contingency	The deliverable was submitted 10 months late.
Task 2.3: Fabrication of irradiated specimens	
Explanation/ Reason	The milestone MS5 and deliverable D2.3 (D4) are delayed. The shipping of the irradiated material to participants was delayed, causing issues to the scheduling with other overlapping work at the participants. The irradiated materials require special attention, and fabrication cannot be sub-contracted. The passing of the project coordinator has delayed progress in general, since the continuation was at a standstill.
Impact on other tasks	The impact on testing in WP3 is expected to be within reason, as all fabrication is expected to be finished in early 2023.
Impact on resources	None
Impact on planning	Moderate delay expected to be compensated for within the next two years of the project.
Corrective Action/ Contingency	The progress was discussed in November 2022 in the 2Y project progress meeting, and most of the participants are expected to finalise the work in Q1 of 2023 (MS5). Participants were surveyed in November 2022 for their status and the experiences so far, with a follow-up survey to be sent in 2023. Work on the deliverable has been started and will be finalised in the weeks following MS5 .
WP3	
Task 3.1: Fracture mechanics testing of mini-CT specimens on unirradiated RPV steels	
Explanation/ Reason	Some test series on unirradiated materials are pending. The reasons are: (i) COVID-19 related delays, (ii) temporary unavailability of test facilities (moving of a lab).
Impact on other tasks	Task T3.3 (as tested samples are needed). The impact is minor, as tested samples from other test series are available.
Impact on resources	None
Impact on planning	Possible delay of Task 3.3 (fractography).

Corrective Action/ Contingency	Not possible.
WP4	
<i>Task 4.1: Fracture mechanics simulations using C(T) specimens</i>	
Explanation/Reason	Milestone MS10 is delayed. Numerous discussions had to be conducted with the various partners to harmonise and synthesise all the contributions, and to organise the future work of the coming months in an efficient and relevant manner.
Impact on other tasks	None
Impact on resources	None
Impact on planning	None
Corrective Action/Contingency	The milestone was achieved but the report is 4 months late. The first draft is available and the final version is expected by 31-01-2023.
WP5	
No deviations	
WP6	
<i>Task 6.1: Training and education</i>	
Explanation/ Reason	The first FRACTESUS special session (corresponding to D6.4 (D21) and MS17) will be completed at the ASME PVP 2023 conference (July 2023). Then, the actual date is four months behind of the schedule, from m30 to m34. However, this was agreed by the complete FRACTESUS consortium due to the great impact of the ASME PVP conference. In addition, the delay does not affect the correct development of the project.
Impact on other tasks	None
Impact on resources	None
Impact on planning	None

Corrective Action/ Contingency	None
WP7	
Task 7.2: Administration (deliverables, milestones, financial reporting)	
Explanation/ Reason	Efficient management and timely administration was delayed due to the sudden death of the project coordinator.
Impact on other tasks	The project was not efficiently managed in Q2-Q3 of 2022.
Impact on resources	Possible overhead for the settling-in of the new coordinator will be carried by SCK CEN.
Impact on planning	Delayed actions by 3-4 months.
Corrective Action/ Contingency	The resulting impact on the overall progress of the project is minor and expected to be mitigated during the remainder of the project.
WP8	
No deviations	

8 Project Scientific Output

8.1 Presentations and proceedings at international conferences

- 1) **1st Virtual European Conference on Fracture, 29 June – 1 July 2020, Online (presentation + paper)**
 - S. Cicero, M. Lambrecht, H. Swan, P. Arffman, E. Altstadt, T. Petit, F. Obermeier, B. Arroyo, J.A. Álvarez, R. Lacalle. Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens: FRACTESUS project. Procedia Structural Integrity 28, pp. 61-66 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2020.10.008>
- 2) **ASME Pressure Vessels & Piping Conference, 13–15 July 2021, Online (presentation + paper)**
 - Brynk, T, Lambrecht, M, Uytendhouwen, I, Arffman, P, Altstadt, E, & Petit, T. FRACTESUS Project: General Framework of Materials Selection and Testing Processes. Proceedings of ASME PVP Conference 2021. Volume 4: Materials and Fabrication. Virtual, Online. July 13-15, 2021. V004T06A066. ASME. <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2021-61906>
- 3) **20th International Conference on Fusion Reactor Materials, 24–29 October 2021, Online (presentation only)**
 - S. Cicero, “FRACTESUS project: an european effort to validate the use of sub-sized specimens in fracture mechanics testing of irradiated materials”

- 4) 5th Iberian Conference on Structural Integrity, 30 March – 1 April 2022, Coimbra, Portugal (presentation + paper)**
 - M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo. FRACTESUS: fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens. *Revista Española de Mecánica de la Fractura*. Volumen 3, pp. 65-70, 2022. ISSN: 2792-4246.
- 5) 31st International Conference on Metallurgy and Materials, 18–19 May 2022, Brno, Czech Republic (presentation + paper)**
 - G. Dundulis, E. Narvydas, V. Leišis, T. Petit. Estimation of the loading conditions to fracture behaviour. *Proceedings of the 31st Int. Conf. Metall. Mater.*, 2022: pp. 370–375. <https://doi.org/10.37904/metal.2022.4409>
- 6) European Conference on Fracture, 27 June – 1 July 2022, Madeira, Portugal (2 presentations + 2 papers)**
 - M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, S. Arrieta. Master curve evaluation of ANP-5 steel using mini-CT specimens. *Procedia Structural Integrity* (Accepted, in press).
 - M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, S. Arrieta. FRACture mechanics TESting of irradiated RPV steels by means of SUB-sized Specimens: FRACTESUS PROJECT. *Procedia Structural Integrity* (Accepted, in press).
- 7) ASME Pressure Vessels & Piping Conference, 17–22 July 2022, Las Vegas, USA (presentation + paper)**
 - Brynk, T, Uytendhouwen, I, Arffman, P, Altstadt, E, Kopriva, R, Obermeier, F, & Serrano, M. FRACTESUS Project: Final Selection of RPV Materials for Unirradiated and Irradiated Round Robins. *Proceedings of ASME PVP Conference 2022. Volume 1: Codes and Standards*. Las Vegas, Nevada, USA. July 17–22, 2022. V001T01A026. ASME. <https://doi.org/10.1115/PVP2022-83871>
- 8) 10th Euratom Conference on Reactor Safety & 10th Euratom Conference Radioactive Waste Management, 30 May – 3 June 2022, Lyon, France (presentation + paper)**
 - T. Brynk, F.J. Perosanz, A. McLennan. Increase of nuclear installations safety by better understanding of materials performance and new testing techniques development (MEACTOS, INCEFA-SCALE, and FRACTESUS H2020 projects). *EPJ Nuclear Science and Technology*, Volume 8, 42, 2022.
- 9) 27th International Conference on Fracture and Structural Integrity, 22–24 February 2023, Rome, Italy (accepted abstract)**
 - M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo, G. Bonny, H. Swan, P. Lappalainen, E. Altstadt, T. Petit, FRACTESUS Project overview: objectives, organisation and initial findings.
- 10) ASME Pressure Vessels & Piping Conference 2023, 16–21 July 2023, Atlanta, USA (5 accepted abstracts)**
 - G. Bonny, E. Altstadt, P. Arffman, S. Cicero, F. Obermeier, T. Petit, H. Swan, T. Brynk, R. Chaouadi, P. Lappalainen, M. Li, M. Serrano, B. Tanguy, I. Uytendhouwen, H. Wilcox. Present status of the FRACTESUS project: Towards fracture toughness miniaturization of nuclear steels
 - M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo. Fracture characterization of structural steel S275JR by using conventional CT specimens, mini-CT specimens and Small Punch specimens: a comparison
 - M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, S. Arrieta. Methodological alternatives when dealing with mini-CT specimens to characterize the ductile-to-brittle transition zone

- T. Metzler, E. Gaganidze, J. Aktaa. Numerical prediction of fracture toughness of a reactor pressure vessel steel based on experiments using small specimens
- M. Li, R. Chaouadi, I. Uytendhouwen, T. Pardoen, T. Brynk, G. Bonny. The Effect of Loss of Constraint on the Initiation of Ductile Fracture in a Mini-Ct

11) 7th International Conference of Engineering Against Failure, 21–23 June 2023, Spetses, Greece (accepted abstract)

- M. Sánchez, S. Cicero, B. Arroyo. Fracture characterization of structural steel S690Q by using mini-CT specimens

8.2 Presentations and proceedings at national conferences

1) 37° Congress of Spanish Group of Fracture, 7–8 June 2021, Online (presentation + paper)

- B. Arroyo, S. Cicero, M. Lambrecht, H. Swan, P. Arffman, E. Altstadt, T. Petit, F. Obermeier. Caracterización en fractura de aceros de vasija mediante probetas mini-ct y small punch. Primeros pasos del proyecto europeo FRACTESUS. Revista Española de Mecánica de la Fractura. Volumen 2, pp. 49-54, 2021. ISSN: 2792-4246.

8.3 Peer Reviewed Journal Papers

- 1) E. Altstadt, F. Bergner, M. Houska. Use of the small punch test for the estimation of ductile-to-brittle transition temperature shift of irradiated steels. Nuclear materials and energy 26, 100918 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nme.2021.100918>.

9 Project Financials

A financial summary after the first reporting period (RP1) is provided in *Table 4*. In the table, the total project cost per partner and EC contributions are indicated for both the initial grant agreement and after the amendment of 17/07/2020. The pre-financing and first payment to all partners is also summarized. The column “% accepted EU Amendm1” indicates the percentage of the total budget used during RP1. All partners remain engaged to complete all deliverables as described within the grant agreement and within the agreed budget. In any case, possible overspending cannot be charged to the EC.

Table 4 – Financial summary after the first reporting period.

#	Beneficiary	Total costs	EC Funding à 100%	EC Funding DoW	%	Pre-financing		Budget 2020-07-17 _ Amendm 1				Period 1 Costs			First payment		
						Amount	%	Total costs	Max EU contribution	EC Funding DoW	%	Accepted costs	Accepted EU contribution, following DoW	% accepted EU Amendm 1	Payment November 2022	Total paid	Total paid in %
1	SCK	1,104,612.50	1,104,612.50	706,675.00	63.97%	341,559.59	48.33%	1,104,612.50	1,104,612.50	706,675.00	63.97%	300,751.19	192,390.53	27.22%	228,506.36	570,065.95	80.67%
2	NRI	180,843.75	180,843.75	126,575.00	69.99%	61,177.92	48.33%	180,843.75	126,590.63	126,575.00	69.99%	71,264.54	49,879.02	39.41%	40,928.56	102,106.48	80.67%
3	VTT	193,330.00	193,330.00	193,330.00	100.00%	93,442.83	48.33%	193,330.00	193,330.00	193,330.00	100.00%	52,400.89	52,400.89	27.10%	62,514.09	155,956.92	80.67%
4	CEA	466,433.75	466,433.75	250,767.38	53.76%	121,204.23	48.33%	466,433.75	466,433.75	250,767.38	53.76%	164,820.36	88,611.88	35.34%	81,086.71	202,290.94	80.67%
5	IRSN	175,000.00	175,000.00	87,500.00	50.00%		0.00%	175,000.00	175,000.00	87,500.00	50.00%	24,321.91	12,160.96	13.90%	70,585.17	70,585.17	80.67%
6	FRA-G	256,625.00	256,625.00	170,375.00	66.39%	82,347.92	48.33%	256,625.00	179,367.50	170,375.00	66.39%	126,613.74	84,058.86	49.34%	55,091.48	137,439.40	80.67%
7	HZDR	308,516.25	308,516.25	211,375.00	68.51%	102,164.58	48.33%	308,516.25	308,516.25	211,375.00	68.51%	93,350.51	75,927.89	35.92%	68,349.01	170,513.59	80.67%
8	KIT	143,795.00	143,795.00	143,794.38	100.00%	69,500.62	48.33%	143,795.00	143,795.00	143,794.38	100.00%	114,454.59	114,454.59	79.60%	46,496.52	115,997.14	80.67%
9	BZN	144,187.50	144,187.50	144,187.50	100.00%	69,690.63	48.33%	144,187.50	144,187.50	144,187.50	100.00%	25,622.09	25,622.09	17.77%	46,623.64	116,314.27	80.67%
10	EK	109,375.00	109,375.00	100,375.00	91.77%	48,514.58	48.33%	109,375.00	109,375.00	100,375.00	91.77%	30,855.16	28,315.78	28.21%	32,456.69	80,971.27	80.67%
11	KTU	41,250.00	41,250.00	32,500.00	78.79%	15,708.33	48.33%	41,250.00	41,250.00	32,500.00	78.79%	14,581.30	11,488.30	35.35%	10,509.02	26,217.35	80.67%
12	NRG	244,062.50	244,062.50	236,950.00	97.09%	114,525.83	48.33%	244,062.50	244,062.50	236,950.00	97.09%	89,998.31	87,379.36	36.88%	76,618.80	191,144.63	80.67%
13	STUBA	62,500.00	62,500.00	31,250.00	50.00%	15,104.17	48.33%	62,500.00	62,500.00	31,250.00	50.00%	9,270.68	4,635.34	14.83%	10,104.82	25,208.99	80.67%
14	CIEMAT	87,875.00	87,875.00	86,500.00	98.44%	41,808.33	48.33%	87,875.00	87,875.00	86,500.00	98.44%	34,532.64	33,992.32	39.30%	27,970.15	69,778.48	80.67%
15	UC	268,750.00	268,750.00	141,628.12	52.70%	68,453.59	48.33%	268,750.00	268,750.00	141,628.12	52.70%	110,933.28	58,461.84	41.28%	45,796.06	114,249.65	80.67%
16	PSI	99,250.00	99,250.00	73,900.00	74.46%	35,718.33	48.33%	99,250.00	99,250.00	73,900.00	74.46%	24,640.40	18,346.85	24.83%	23,895.88	59,614.21	80.67%
17	NNL	84,790.00	84,790.00	53,866.88	63.53%	26,035.66	48.33%	84,790.00	59,353.00	53,866.88	63.53%	25,443.01	16,163.89	30.01%	17,418.08	43,453.74	80.67%
18	UoB	233,750.00	233,750.00	71,250.00	30.48%	34,437.50	48.33%	233,750.00	233,750.00	71,250.00	30.48%	1,429.95	435.87	0.61%	23,038.99	57,476.49	80.67%
19	CCFE	214,865.00	214,865.00	124,015.35	57.72%	59,940.75	48.33%	214,865.00	214,865.00	124,015.35	57.72%	20,049.39	11,073.00	8.93%	40,100.90	100,041.65	80.67%
20	CRIEPI		0.00						0.00								
21	ORNL		0.00						0.00								
22	CNL		0.00						0.00								
TOTAL		4,419,811.25	4,419,811.25	2,986,814.61		1,401,335.39		4,419,811.25	4,262,863.63	2,986,814.61		1,335,333.94	965,799.26		1,008,090.93	2,409,426.32	

This project has received funding from the Euratom research and training programme 2020-2024 under grant agreement No 900014.

10 Conclusion

The project has run half of its duration and continues as planned with minor deviations. All planned milestones and deliverables were executed and provided except for milestone **MS5** and deliverables **D2.3 (D4)** and **D3.1 (D5)**. However, they are all close to completion and their impact on the other tasks within the project are minimal. The most impacting deviation encountered in the project was the sudden death of the project leader, which led to a loss of managing efficiency during several months. The resulting delays are expected to be resolved throughout the remainder of the project.

The objectives described in Annex 1 of the grant agreement remain relevant, which was confirmed during the surveys taken with nuclear regulatory bodies, operators and research organizations (see deliverable **D1.1**). All partners have contributed and continue to contribute, in close collaboration with each other, to the realization of the project objectives.

The project has disseminated its results through social media, scientific literature and events, as well as in other EC funded (ENTENTE, STRUMAT-LTO, DELISA-LTO) and national projects (Kleinproben).

The financial summary after the first reporting period indicates no major deviations and all partners remain engaged to complete all deliverables as described within the grant agreement and within the agreed budget.

